

Automatic Language Translation 50 Years Ago

Demonstration of a U.S. Machine Translation System at the University of Zurich

An important field of artificial intelligence, which was generously supported financially, was machine translation. The source language was often Russian, and the target language, for example, English. Despite years of effort, a real breakthrough never materialized. Research in this field was carried out at numerous universities in North America, Asia and Europe in the 1970s. In 1975, the US Systran translation system was demonstrated at three locations in Europe: at the University of Bonn in Germany, before the European Communities (EC) Commission in Luxembourg, and at the University of Zurich. The software was developed by Latsec Inc., in La Jolla, California.

By Herbert Bruderer

Demonstration of a Californian translation program in Zurich

The only extensively documented presentation was the demonstration in the Department of Informatics at the University of Zurich (see Fig. 1). Obtaining machine-readable Russian texts posed a considerable problem (see Fig. 2). These texts had to be initially converted from the Cyrillic to the Latin alphabet according to specific rules (see Fig. 3). The University of Grenoble (France), which was developing a Russian-French translation system at this time, ultimately provided suitable text material, stored on a heavy magnetic tape. It had to be collected in person in France and cleared through customs upon import in Geneva. The scientific and technical documents comprised approximately 100,000 words (about 300 A4 pages), which were then stored to punched cards in Zurich. The experiment utilized around 30,000 words, and the roughly 100 pages were automatically translated in 6 minutes (pure machine time). The quality of the raw translations was satisfactory (see Fig. 4). The translation program was stored on a stack of magnetic discs. Magnetic tapes and magnetic discs served as storage media (see Fig. 5). The demonstration took place at the computer center of the University of Zurich on an IBM 370-155 mainframe computer with 1536 K core memory (see Fig. 6). The EC made use of Systran for an extended period of time and held several international conferences on this topic. Systran was rule-based and comprised several comprehensive dictionaries.

Fig. 1: Cover of the *Handbuch der maschinellen und maschinenunterstützten Sprachübersetzung. Automatische Übersetzung natürlicher Sprachen und mehrsprachige Terminologiedatenbanken* (Handbook of machine translation and machine-aided translation. Automatic translation of natural languages and multilingual terminology databases), K. G. Saur Verlag KG, Munich, New York, London, Paris 1978, 880 pages

POLOCAET VOZMOZHNOST6 PROGNOZIROVAT6 DAL6NEIWE RAZYITIE TOT CASTI C\$SELENNOI ,
V KOTOROI NAXODITS4 NAWA PLANETA . C\$OSOBYI INTERES NAR4DU S IZUCENIEM C\$SOLNQA
I PLANET PREDSTAVL4ET ISSLEDOVANIE ASTEROIDOV , KOTORYE , KAK PREDPOLAGAHT
NEKOTORYE UCENYE , 4VL4HTS4 OSTATKAMI PLANETY , NEKOGDA SUSESTVOVAVWEI MEJDU
ORBITAMI C\$MARSA I C\$HPITERA I RAZRUWIVWEIS4 (ILI RAZRUWENNOI) PRI ZAGADOCNYX
OBSTO4TEL6STVAX . C\$SEIICAS UJE DOSTOVERNO IZVESTNO , CTO ASTEROIDY IMEHT 4RKO
VYRAJENNUH OSKOLOCNUH FORMU . C\$A VED6 MOJET STAT6S4 , KAK 3TO NI MALOVERO4TNO
. CTO NA ISCEZNUVWEI PLANETE BYLA JIZN6 . I , MOJET BYT6 , DAJE RAZUMNA4 .
C\$KATASTROFU OTNOS4T KO VREMENI , OTSTO4SEMU OT NAWIX DNEI NA 75 MILLIONOV LET
. C\$POSLE VYSADKI 3KSPEDIQII NA ASTEROIDY , OSOBEENO NA TAKIE KRUPNYE , KAK
C\$QERERA , C\$VESTA I DRUGIE , UCENYE SUMEHT OTVETIT6 NA VOPROS , SUSESTVOVALA
LI TAM JIZN6 . C\$PROGRESS KOSMONAVTIKI TAK STREMITELN , CTO MNOGIE SAMYE
FANTASTICESKIE IDEI INOGDA NE POSPEVAHT ZA REAL6NYMI SVERWENI4MI . C\$BESSPOREN
TOT FAKT , CTO CELOVECESTVO STOIT NA POROGE OSVOENI4 DAL6NEGO KOSMOSA . C\$RIS .
1 . C\$ORIFNTIROVOCNYE 3NERGETICESKIE ZATRATY DL4 POLETOV K PLANETAM SOLNECNOI
SISTEMY . 1 _ ZONDY K PLANETAM . 2 _ OBLET PLANET . 3 _ OBLET S VYXODOM NA
PLANETOQENTRICESKUH ORBITU . 4 _ 3KSPEDIQII NA PLANETY ILI IX SPUTNIKI . 5 6
C\$MASWTAB 7 C\$MERKURII 8 C\$VENERA 9 C\$MARS 10 C\$LUNA 11 C\$NEPTUN 12
C\$URAN 13 C\$SATURN 14 C\$HPITER C\$RIS . 2 . C\$ORIENTIROVOCNYE VESOVYE
XARAKTERISTIKI KOSMICESKIX APPARATOV DL4 ISSLEDOVANI4 PLANET . 1 C\$S
ISPOL6ZOVANIEM PERSPEKTIVNYX . 2 C\$S ISPOL6ZOVANIEM . 3 C\$S ISPOL6ZOVANIEM .
1 . 2 . 3 . 4 _ ZADACI , UKAZANNYE NA RIS . 1 . 5 C\$MASWTAB 6 C\$HPITER 7
C\$SATURN 8 C\$VENERA 9 C\$LUNA 10 C\$MARS 11 C\$MERKURII C\$VESOVYE XARAKTERISTIKI
KOSMICESKIX APPARATOV DL4 REWENI4 R4DA ZADAC PO C\$VENERE , C\$MERKURIH ,
C\$HPITERU I C\$SATURNU VYXOD4T ZA PREDELY DIAGRAMMY . C\$RIS . 3 .
C\$ORIENTIROVOCNYI VES 3KSPEDIQIONNYX KOMPLEKSOV DL4 POLETOV K C\$LUNE , C\$MARSU
. C\$VENERE , C\$MERKURIH I SPUTNIKAM C\$SATURNA I C\$HPITERA . C\$RAZBROS
NACAL6NOGO VESA POLUCEN PRI ISPOL6ZOVANII RAZLICNYX TIPOV RAKETNYX DVIGATELEI
I . 1 C\$VES NA ORBITE 2 C\$HPITER 3 C\$SATURN 4 C\$MERKURII 5 C\$VENERA 6 C\$MARS 7
C\$LUNA C\$RIS . 4 . C\$SOPOSTAVLENIE RAZMEROV I VESA PERSPEKTIVNYX RAKET -
NOSITELEI S VYSOCALWIM V MIRE SOORUJENIEM : C\$OSTANKINSKOI BAWNEI (530 M) .
C\$RAZBROS STARTOVYX VESOV 4VL4ETS4 SLEDSTVIEM PRIMENENI4 DVIGATELEI RAZLICNYX
TIPOV NA KOSMICESKIX STUPEN4X I RAKETE - NOSITELE , PRICEM MINIMAL6NYI VES
SOOTVETSTVUET ISPOL6ZOVANI4 I , A MAKSIMAL6NYI _ . C\$GABARITY RAKET DL4
ODNOI I TOI JE ZADACI PRI 3TOM DOVOL6NO BLIZKI . 1 C\$SATURN - 5 ; VES _ 2700 T
DL4 C\$LUNY . 2 C\$VES _ 6000 - 30000 T DL4 C\$MARSA . 3 C\$VES _ 10000 - 45000 T
DL4 C\$VENERY . 4 C\$VES _ 12000 - 90000 T DL4 C\$MERKURII . 5 C\$VES _ 45000 -
180000 T DL4 C\$SATURNA . 6 C\$VES _ 70000 - 250000 T DL4 C\$HPITERA . C\$RIS . 5 .
C\$XEMA STYKOVKI VZAIMOZAMEN4EMYX BLOKOV : _ VYVOD I PROVERKA FUNKCIONIROVANI4
BLOKA ; _ SBLIJENIE (DUBLIRUETS4) ; _ STYKOVKA OCEREDNOGO BLOKA S KARAVANOM
; _ RASSTYKOVKA OTKAZAVWEGO BLOKA S KARAVANOM C\$RIS . 6 C\$OJIDAEMYE POTERI
BLOKOV PRI STYKOVKE . 1 _ SLUCAI MINIMAL6NYX POTER6 ; 2 _ SLUCAI MAKSIMAL6NYX
POTER6 . C\$V OBOIX SLUCA4X ISPOL6ZUHTS4 SISTEMY S ODINAKOVOI NADEJNOST6H . 3
KOLICESTVO ISPOL6ZOVANNYX BLOKOV I NOSITELEI 4 DVUKRATNA4 STYKOVKA 5
ODNOKRATNA4 STYKOVKA 6 VERO4TNOST6 USPEWNOI STYKOVKI

C\$VLI4NIE C\$KOMPOOVKI C\$SAMOLETA , C\$REJIMA C\$EGO C\$POLETA C\$I C\$SOSTO4NI4
C\$ATMOSFERY C\$NA C\$INTENSIVNOST6 C\$ZVUKOVOGO C\$UDARA C\$ANALIZ VLI4NI4
KOMPOOVKI SAMOLETA , REJIMA EGO POLETA I SOSTO4NI4 ATMOSFERY NA RASPREDELENIE
IZBYTOCNOGO DAVLENI4 NA BLIZKIX RASSTO4NI4X OT SAMOLETA USLOJN4ETS4 TEM , CTO
RASPREDELENIE DAVLENI4 ZAVISIT OT BOL6WOGO CISLA PARAMETROV , XARAKTERIZUH5IX
FORMU SAMOLETA , TRAEKTORIH EGO POLETA I SOSTO4NIE ATMOSFERY . C\$3TOT ANALIZ
UPRO5AETS4 V SLUCAE BOL6WIX RASSTO4NI4 , KOGDA MOJNO OTDEL6NO ISSLEDOVAT6
VLI4NIE KOMPOOVKI SAMOLETA NA INTENSIVNOST6 - OBRAZNOI VOLNY . C\$TAKIE
ISSLEDOVANI4 PROVODILIS6 V RABOTAX C\$MORRISA (1) , C\$RAIMINGA I C\$UOLERA (2
) I DR . C\$V 3TIX RABOTAX ANALIZIROVALOS6 VLI4NIE NA INTENSIVNOST6 ZVUKOVOGO
UDARA RASPREDELENI4 PODTEMNOI SILY DL4 IZOLIROVANNYX KRYL6EV RAZLICNOI FORMY V

Fig. 2: Excerpt from the Russian source text provided by the University of Grenoble, France. Source: Handbuch der maschinellen und maschinenunterstützten Sprachübersetzung. Automatische Übersetzung natürlicher Sprachen und mehrsprachige Terminologiedatenbanken, K. G. Saur Verlag KG, München, New York, London, Paris 1978, page 569

A	A	P	R
Б	B	С	S
В	V	Т	T
Г	G	У	U
Д	D	Ф	F
Е	E	Х	X
Ж	J	Ц	Q
З	Z	Ч	C
И	I	Ш	W
Й	1	Щ	5
К	K	Ъ	7
Л	L	Ы	Y
М	M	Ь	6
Н	N	Э	3
О	O	Ю	H
П	P	Я	4

Fig. 3: Rules for converting the Cyrillic text. Source: Handbuch der maschinellen und maschinenunterstützten Sprachübersetzung. Automatische Übersetzung natürlicher Sprachen und mehrsprachige Terminologiedatenbanken, K. G. Saur Verlag KG, München, New York, London, Paris 1978, page 190

SUBJECT CODE 4G

THE INFLUENCE OF THE LAYOUT OF AN AIRCRAFT, MODE OF ITS MISSION AND
CONDITION OF THE ATMOSPHERE IN THE INTENSITY OF A SONIC BOOM THE
ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF THE LAYOUT OF AN AIRCRAFT, MODE OF ITS
MISSION AND CONDITION OF THE ATMOSPHERE IN THE DISTRIBUTION OF
OVERPRESSURE AT NEAR DISTANCES FROM AN AIRCRAFT IS COMPLICATED BY THE
FACT THAT PRESSURE ALLOCATION DEPENDS ON THE LARGE NUMBER OF
PARAMETERS, WHICH CHARACTERIZE THE FORM OF AN AIRCRAFT, THE TRAJECTORY
OF ITS FLIGHT AND THE CONDITION OF THE ATMOSPHERE. THIS ANALYSIS IS
SIMPLIFIED IN THE CASE OF LARGE DISTANCES, WHEN IT IS POSSIBLE
SEPARATELY TO INVESTIGATE THE INFLUENCE OF THE LAYOUT OF AN AIRCRAFT
ON INTENSITY - A DESCRIPTIVE WAVE. SUCH RESEARCH WAS CONDUCTED IN THE
WORKS OF MORRIS (1), RAYMINGA AND UOLERA (2), ETC. IN THESE WORKS THE
INFLUENCE ON THE INTENSITY OF THE SONIC BOOM OF LIFT DISTRIBUTION FOR
THE ISOLATED WINGS OF A DIFFERENT PLANFORM, THE INFLUENCE OF THE FORM
OF THE ISOLATED BODY OF REVOLUTION, AND ALSO THE INFLUENCE OF AN
ENTIRE COMBINATION AS A WHOLE WAS ANALYZED. IN JONES' WORK (3) WAS
OBTAINED THE LOWER BOUNDARY OF INTENSITY - A DESCRIPTIVE WAVE AT THE

Fig. 4: English target text in the form of a rough translation, produced at the University of Zurich on June 13, 1975. Source: Handbuch der maschinellen und maschinenunterstützten Sprachübersetzung. Automatische Übersetzung natürlicher Sprachen und mehrsprachige Terminologiedatenbanken, K. G. Saur Verlag KG, München, New York, London, Paris 1978, page 579

360-65 SYSTRAN TRANSLATION PROCESSING

Quelle:
 Peter P. Toma, Ludek A. Kozlik, Donald G. Perwin, Optimization of SYSTRAN System, Latsec Incorporated, RADC-TR-72-73, Final Technical Report, April 1972, S. 14, vgl. [324]
 14

Fig. 5: Data flow chart of the Systran system: The rectangles indicate processing steps, while the circles stand for magnetic tapes, and the cylinders represent magnetic discs. Source: Handbuch der maschinellen und maschinenunterstützten Sprachübersetzung. Automatische Übersetzung natürlicher Sprachen und mehrsprachige Terminologiedatenbanken, K. G. Saur Verlag KG, München, New York, London, Paris 1978, page 192

Fig. 6: Section of the computing machinery at the data center of the University of Zurich (as of June 1975). The devices in use are shaded. Today's smartphone is much more powerful than a mainframe computer of that time. Source Handbuch der maschinellen und maschinenunterstützten Sprachübersetzung. Automatische Übersetzung natürlicher Sprachen und mehrsprachige Terminologiedatenbanken, K. G. Saur Verlag KG, München, New York, London, Paris 1978, page 195

Technical terms

Bandeinheit	tape unit
Kartenleser	punched card reader
Kartenstanzer	card punch
Plattenspeicher	magnetic disc storage
Plattenstapel	magnetic disc pack
Schnelldrucker	high-speed printer
Schreibdichte	recording density
Spur	track

This article is based on the following work (see Figs. 7 and 8):

Fig. 7: Herbert Bruderer: Wendepunkte in der analogen und digitalen Welt. Von der Tontafel zur künstlichen Intelligenz, De Gruyter Oldenbourg, Berlin, Boston 2026, 432 Seiten, 533 Abbildungen (90% farbig), 34 Tabellen

Fig. 8: Herbert Bruderer. Turning Points in the Analog and Digital World. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, 2026, 520 pages, 533 illustrations (90% in color), 34 tables.

For more information please see:

Bruderer, H. (2026). Turning Points in the Analog and Digital World. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17822921>
 ACM, New York

Bruderer, H. (2026). Wendepunkte in der analogen und digitalen Welt. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17455914>
 De Gruyter, Berlin

Bruderer, H. (2026). Bruderer: Short list of books on the history of science and technology, March 2026. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18778447>

© Bruderer Informatik, CH-9401 Rorschach, Switzerland 2026
 Translated from the original German by John McMinn

Herbert Bruderer
 Seehaldenstrasse 26
 Postfach 47
 CH-9401 Rorschach
 Switzerland
 +41 71 855 77 11
herbert.bruderer@bluewin.ch
bruderer@retired.ethz.ch

March, 26, 2026